

Problem-Solving With Algorithms A Disciplinary Commons Portfolio

Carlos A. Perez-Delgado, University of Kent
c.perez@kent.ac.uk

1 Summary

This is a module portfolio for University of Kent's COMP3830: Problem-solving with Algorithms. This is a first-year undergraduate module that aims to introduce students to the discipline of theoretical computer science; allow them to make an informed decision as to whether to (continue to) pursue a career in this discipline; and give them fundamental tools they will need if they decide to do so. The module introduces the basic concepts of *algorithm*, algorithm correctness, and runtime analysis.

2 Context

2.1 The University of Kent

The University of Kent is a semi-collegiate research university based in Canterbury, Kent. It was granted a royal charter on 4 January 1965.

The university's main campus is situated on the north end of Canterbury and consists of roughly 300 acres (1.2 km²) of park land, housing over 6,000 students.

The University of Kent has a strong computer science research presence. It is one of nineteen universities recognised as a national Academic Centre of Excellence in Cybersecurity Research (ACE-CSR), a certification jointly issued by EPSRC and the NCSC. It is also part of the National Hub for Quantum Communications research.

2.2 School of Computing

The School of Computing admits roughly three hundred students a year, in total, across six different programs: Computer Science BSc, Computer Science (Cybersecurity) BSc, Data Science BSc, Software Engineering BSc, Artificial Intelligence BSc, and Business Information Technology BSc.

Of the six programs, three (CS, CS (Cybersecurity), and Software Engineering) differ only in their final year modules. All six programs share a large portion of modules.

All programs require a minimum A level of 'BBB.' The Data Science program further requires a mathematics A level, but no other program currently does. All programs also admit students with BTEC, International Baccalaureate, and other accreditations.

All programs are three-year programs, with an option to do an extra "year in industry." This is an opportunity for the student to be employed at a partner vetted company. This extra year is added between the usual second and third academic years.

2.3 COMP3830: Problem-Solving with Algorithms

The module in this portfolio serves as a first-year introduction to algorithms, data-structures, and problem-solving within the domain of computer science. The module is mandatory for students of all programs offered in the School of Computing, except for Business IT, and Data Science students. It is taught in the second term of the first year. In the first term, students learn basic programming principles in Java, and fundamental mathematics concepts such as powers and logarithms, which are essential to the understanding of the module's material.

The module was first taught in 2020. In 2018 the School of Computing faculty decided to address a long-standing issue of poor student performance in the second year, in particular in the more theoretical modules/topics: algorithms, complexity theory, and formal languages and automata theory.

The overwhelming consensus, at the time, was that the difficulty increase between first and second year were too steep, and students were arriving to these more advanced/abstract modules with little preparation.

The idea was pitched to create a module that would both serve as a grand overview of the academic discipline that is computer science, and also provide a more gentle introduction to some of its more challenging concepts.

The module is designed to be taught in the second term of the first year, so that its delivery can assume basic knowledge of programming, and CS fundamentals, from the students.

This includes the use of a text-editor and compiler (or interpreter) to run code, basic coding in any language of choice, including variable declaration and assignments, basic control/flow structures, methods/functions, and basic I/O in the UNIX runtime environment. Students are also expected to have a decent understanding of basic mathematical concepts, such as functions, logarithms and exponentials, basic logic and set theory.

By the end of the module, students are expected to be ready to undertake more advanced modules in complexity theory, algorithms, and theory of computing.

2.4 Staffing and Operational Details

The teaching of COMP3830 is led by Carlos A. Perez-Delgado. Dr. Perez-Delgado is the member of the School of Computing who first proposed the module, and then went on to develop the original module specification. He also teaches 'Introduction to Cybersecurity and Cryptography,' in the second year, and 'Introduction to Quantum Computing and Quantum Cryptography,' which is a final year and post-graduate module offered in both the School of Computing, and School of Physical Sciences.

Dr. Perez-Delgado has a first degree in computer science, a Master of Mathematics in Combinatorics and Optimisation, and a PhD in quantum computing. He has helped develop quantum models of computation, quantum algorithms and data-structures, quantum cryptographic protocols, a quantum software engineering modelling language, as well other quantum information-theoretic tools.

3 Content

In brief, the module aims to arm the student with an overarching view of the discipline of theoretical computer science, and prepare them to succeed in more in-depth and advanced modules in these topics taught in later years.

The module introduces the following major topics: algorithms and data structures, computational complexity theory, and very briefly, computability theory. The emphasis is on problem-solving. The aim is to not merely teach the students *about* the topics, but rather train them to use these concepts to solve real-world problems.

By the end of the module, students should be able to

1. Read a problem description
2. Design an algorithmic solution to the problem, and describe it in pseudocode
3. Reason, in a rudimentary fashion, about the correctness of the program
4. Do simple complexity analysis of the algorithm, and express that complexity in 'Big O' notation.
5. Implement the algorithm in a language of their choice, under the UNIX runtime environment

A sample problem that students are tasked with solving is given in the teaching methods section. The problem there showcases well the expectations and requirements of the module. To succeed, a student

needs to read the description, understand the task to be accomplished, effectively sieve the important details from the unimportant ones, design a 'solution' program, and implement it in code.

The module is organised roughly into three parts. The first is a general introduction to computer science. This first part focuses on introducing students to the *how* and *why* of the study of algorithms. It introduces the use pseudo-code to present and study algorithms, and big 'oh' notation to study and describe their runtime. It also introduces the students to the notions that some problems are infeasible to compute, and others are completely uncomputable.

This part of the module uses the history of algorithms and computer science as a pedagogical tool. This approach grounds the more theoretical aspects of the module, and provides context for the taught content.

This first part leads naturally into the second part of the module, where algorithms and algorithmic techniques are discussed. First, the notion of 'divide and conquer' as an over-arching technique is introduced. With it, recursion as an effective method to apply this technique is discussed.

The discussion of recursive algorithms then leads to the third and final part: recursive data structures. This includes linked-lists, and binary trees, as well as graphs.

For parts two and three of the module, two textbooks are used as required reading material. The first is '*Algorithms*' by Jeff Erickson and available online, for free, in its entirety at: <http://jeffe.cs.illinois.edu/teaching/algorithms/>. Besides the fact that being easily available makes it more likely to actually be used by students, this text is chosen because it closely matches both the order of topics covered from week three onwards, and generally the depth with which they are covered. The second text used is '*The algorithm design manual*' by Steven Skiena.

A full itemised list of topics covered, by week, is:

Week 1 Introduction to algorithms, pseudocode, and algorithm correctness

Week 2 Introduction to computability and uncomputability

Week 3 Introduction to complexity theory, big 'oh' notation, and runtime analysis, $O(n^2)$ sorting algorithms

Week 4 Introduction to Divide and Conquer, and Recursion, Mergesort.

Week 5 Introduction to Recursive data-structures

Week 6 Introduction to RAM model of computation, and memory allocation

Week 7 Comparative analysis between linked lists, and arrays

Week 8 More on trees and sorting

Week 9 Introduction to graphs, and graph algorithms

Week 10 Review

4 Delivery Methods

COMP3830 is designed from the ground up based on the maxim that '*one learns by doing.*' As such, one of the main aims of the module is to provide students plenty of opportunity to practice the skills being developed in the lectures.

4.1 AI considered harmful

Before moving on to the main course structure, it is worth commenting on the ever-increasing ubiquitousness of machine-learning/AI in higher education. There are many different reactions to this.

Some have opted to fight the use of AI by use of AI-use detection methods. This is an unwinnable battle. Even if tools exist today that can detect the use of AI in certain cases—and such tools will inarguably get better in the future—the current fast pace of ML development means AI-detections tools are almost certain to lag behind. Cheating detection, in and of itself, is a losing proposition.

Others have opted to *embrace* the use of AI rather than fighting it. They allow the use of AI tools in their modules. The argument for this is two-fold: first, it is hard to impossible to stop students from using AI tools, and second, the industry is moving towards AI use regardless, so students might as well learn to use it.

The response to the above is straightforward. We analogise with calculators. Calculators can be used to automate tedious but trivial tasks, such as small multiplications. They can also perform multiplications that are so large that they are infeasible for humans to complete in any reasonable timeframe. No reasonable person would argue that elementary schoolchildren should therefore forgo learning multiplication, and learn to use calculators instead. We, in higher education, all understand the importance of learning and understanding the basic, fundamental, principles.

Like AI/ML calculators and numerical software are powerful tools. Training students in the proper (advanced) use and development has a long history in higher education, with many courses in STEM fields, including modules in numerical methods, and scientific computing. These advanced modules do not *replace* the teaching of the fundamentals, but rather rely on them. Most modules on *numerical methods* will assume the student knows matrix multiplication, Gauss-Jordan decomposition, and of course basic algebra and arithmetic.

Similarly, we expect the students to understand the basics of algorithmics, problem analysis, program development, *etc.* before they move on to use AI code generation tools. We follow the advice of Zed Shaw in his excellent book *Learn Python the Hard Way*: the best way to learn to program is by using a text editor (no IDE or any other fancy tools) and a command-line compiler/interpreter.

Ultimately, a course/module designer needs to decide the graduate profile they are targeting. Do they expect their graduate to go on to help design/build AI/ML systems, or use them in advanced ways? Then they absolutely need to understand the fundamentals. Or do they foresee their graduates merely as AI/ML end-users? In which case, is it even clear their target audience even requires/benefits from a CS degree?

Our approach to AI/ML in COMP3830 is simple and based on honesty: its use is outright banned¹, and we explain to students why this is the case, using the arguments above.

We test all submissions for cheating with AI, as we test them for plagiarism and other forms of cheating. We use automated tools such as MOSS (<https://theory.stanford.edu/~aiken/moss/>). We understand and accept that our catch rate is less than 100%. We rely on a culture of honesty, and high penalties for those who do get caught cheating, to reduce cheating incidences. It should be stressed that cheating, and hard to detect cheating, is not a new phenomenon with the introduction of large language models.

In short, the use of AI/ML is (should be) considered cheating, and is (should be) handled like any other form of cheating.

4.2 Summary of course structure

The formal contact hours are as follows:

¹To keep this simple, we state that the use of any source of outside help *living or dead* is disallowed.

- 22 hours of lectures: one-hour lectures, twice a week, for eleven weeks
- 11 hours of lab sessions: one-hour sessions, once a week for eleven weeks.
- 11 one-hour optional drop-in sessions, delivered weekly, for eleven weeks.

Two lecturers are involved in the teaching of the module, generally splitting the content into a first- and second-half. See previous section for the content discussion. Lab sessions and drop-in sessions are delivered by teaching assistants, under the guidance supervision of the lecturers.

4.3 Lectures

Lectures are used to introduce the module's concepts, both in algorithms and those involved in problem-solving. The students are not expected to have done any pre-reading before coming to lectures.

Lectures are designed to be as interactive as possible, given the technical hurdles—a 300 student audience in particular. Lecturers will introduce a concept, via problem-solving.

For instance, in order to introduce recursion, we first introduce the Towers of Hanoi. Rather than simply explaining the problem to students, the lecturer brings a physical Tower of Hanoi set. He then attempts to solve the problem for three, four, five, and even more towers with the input and help of the students. Along the way, concepts such as divide-and-conquer and recursion are introduced.

In order to introduce sorting, eight student volunteers are asked to step onto the stage. The students are then sorted by height, with the help and input of the entire audience. Bubblesort and Mergesort are both introduced, and their correctness and runtime analysed this way.

4.4 Worksheets

Worksheets are meant to give students ample opportunity to practice what they have learned. Students will always have one outstanding worksheet they need to be working on.

There are over one hundred questions, spread over two to three worksheets. Questions are divided in two ways: by style/type, and then further by difficulty.

There are three main categories of questions: mind-benders, algorithmic problems, and code analysis. In the first category, questions aim to give students an opportunity to practice their problem-solving skills. All the questions in this category seem like typical questions found in a mind-benders book, but all questions have deeply algorithmic solutions.

The second section has more typical algorithms/complexity questions. Students are given coding problems (*e.g.* given a set of numbers, find the second-largest), and asked to code a program that solves it. The third type of problem tasks students with studying a snippet a code and either giving its output given a certain input, arguing for the correctness of a code (or finding an error in it), or arguing about its runtime.

Worksheet questions are further labelled as '*easy*', '*medium*', or '*challenging*,' depending on their difficulty. Students are expected to be able to solve all easy, and most medium questions. Challenging questions are meant to provide an ongoing challenge to even our most advanced students.

4.5 Assessments

It is a well-known maxim in education that '*assessment drives learning*.' Hence, when assessments are few and far in-between, students will gravitate towards a pattern of completely ignoring the module in question, and '*craming*' when assessments pop up. To combat that, in COMP3830 we implement a strategy we refer to as the '*ABC of Programming: Always Be Coding*'.

There are five assessed assignments. The assignments are spread two weeks apart, and each assignment is set for precisely two weeks. Each of these assignments involves a problem that must be solved

algorithmically. The students are tasked with providing a solution to the problem in the form of a compilable program. Currently, students are requested to submit their solutions in Java, in order to make the module compatible with the rest of the first-year curriculum. However, COMP3830 is itself programming-language agnostic.

Each question is either taken directly, or slightly adapted, from the provided worksheets. An example assignment question is:

Bronze Medal: You have been hired by the organisers of a chess tournament. The tournament has competitors engaging in matches throughout the world. Every single player plays against every other player. Players are awarded points in the following manner: 3 points for winning, 1 point for a tie, no points for losing.

The scores for all players have now been collected. You have been tasked with finding the score of the bronze medallist(s). You are to write a program that reads from standard input a series of space-separated non-negative integers no greater than 32,767. Your program is to then write, to standard output, the integer value corresponding to the score of the bronze medallist.

Note, that multiple contestants can tie with the same score, however, there will only be one gold, silver, and bronze medallist. In the case of ties, the competitor with lowest accumulated time to take their turn wins. Your program need only report the *score* of the bronze medallist.

For example, on input:

```
27 3 9 3 6 27 10 15 8
```

Your program should output:

```
15
```

Students' submissions are then assessed by running them against a battery of inputs. Students get one point for each correct output. Algorithm efficiency is assessed indirectly: students submissions are only given up to 10 seconds to run, before the process is killed. While most tested inputs are small, some are quite large, meant to choke a severely inefficient program.

Importantly, assessment marking and feedback are procedurally separated, on purpose. Marking itself is done automatically. This ensures all students are marked against the same rubric, and with the same standard. This also allows for a total of 5 assessments, for over 300 students each (for a total of over 1500 assessments that need marking), can be marked on time by 1-2 people.

Feedback itself is given in three ways. First, the automatic marker will email the students with a detailed report of the battery of tests their submission was evaluated against; which tests were passed, which were failed, and the nature of the failure (*e.g.* the correct answer *v.s.* the provided answer). This feedback tends to be sufficient for the majority of students.

Further, the lecturer(s) do an assessment '*post-mortem*' for most assessments, discussing possible solutions to the assignment, and common pitfalls.

Last, but not least, one-on-one feedback is offered to each student on each of the assessments during their lab sessions (see next section).

Further, there are two theory assessments, in the form of quizzes. These are meant to test the students knowledge of the more theoretical aspects of the module, such as 'Big O' notation, and algorithm correctness and runtime analysis.

4.6 Lab and Drop-in Sessions

Students are provided with weekly lab sessions to help them work through the worksheets. Students are meant to work on the worksheets mostly in their own time, but these sessions give the opportunity to bring in any questions, and clear up any doubts, they might have.

For students that are particularly struggling, we also provide weekly drop-in sessions. While officially drop-in sessions are held by teaching assistants, the lecturers generally make themselves available during these sessions to answer any student questions.

Importantly, both lab and drop-in sessions serve as the main mechanism to provide assessment feedback to students. Students are encouraged to ask any questions about the assessment, their own submission, and how/why they may have failed to achieve all possible marks.

4.7 Textbook

There are two main textbooks for the Module. The first is '*Algorithms*' by Jeff Erickson <http://jeffe.cs.illinois.edu/teaching/algorithms/> This textbook was chosen because it very closely follows the module's content, and it is available, in its entirety, for free online (legally).

A more advanced textbook, for students who wish to delve further into the course material is '*The Algorithm Design Manual*' by Steven Skiena.